

PHAGE DISPLAY IN DISEASE DIAGNOSIS: FROM ANTIBODY SELECTION TO CLINICAL TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

With the advent of molecular biology, a number of display techniques have been developed for the generation of recombinant antibodies. Phage display remains the most effective technique for generating recombinant antibodies. The key factor driving its success is the resilience of the phage particles, facilitating automation and adaptability to modifications. The production of monospecific binders provides an essential diagnostic tool at a more economical and efficient cost. Recombinant antibodies may be altered with significant versatility, rendering them highly appropriate across various platforms.

KEYWORDS: Phage display, antibody discovery, diagnostics, T7 phage, biopanning, immuno-PCR, single-domain antibodies

INTRODUCTION

Phage display is a potent biotechnological method that enables the production of exogenous polypeptides on the surface of phage particles (Pande et al., 2010). The phage display technique has transformed the domain of protein engineering, significantly influencing antibody engineering. The initial advancement in the evolution of phage display approach, which emerged as a highly effective technological platform for the production of antibody-based therapeutics, was reported in 1985 by George Smith. Smith demonstrated that foreign DNA pieces may be integrated into the gene producing the filamentous phage coat protein III (pIII), produced as peptide-phage fusions. Three years later, Parmley and Smith elucidated that peptide-phage fusions, even at a ratio of one peptide-phage fusion per million wildtype virions, could be enriched through the application of biotinylated antibodies specific to the peptides, a technique termed

biopanning. Later, it was demonstrated that libraries comprising millions of random short peptides produced specific peptides capable of tightly binding to various antibodies, thereby establishing the groundwork for identifying specific peptides for any antibody without prior knowledge of its specificity.

PRINCIPLE OF PHAGE DISPLAY TECHNOLOGY

Phage display is a multi-step process that begins with the design of a library. A classical phage display experiment involves screening a library of various protein variants to identify high-affinity binders to a specific ligand. This process begins with cloning the protein into a phagemid vector or recombinant phage and confirming its functional expression on the surface of the generated phage particles.

1. Library construction

A diversified library of DNA sequences that encode target proteins